

THE IMPORTANCE OF INCREASING LEGAL KNOWLEDGE OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION

Firdavs Abdukarimov

1st year student, Faculty of treatment, Tashkent Medical Academy

Nilufar Shomuratovna Niyozova

Scientific supervisor:

Ph.D., Associate Professor, Department of Social
Sciences, Tashkent Medical Academy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14415766>

Annotation

This article pays special attention to the meaning of the concept of corruption, the content of the anti-corruption law adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the role of youth in the fight against this evil. The conditions created in our country for training young people and increasing their intellectual potential will also be discussed.

Key words: youth, corruption, struggle, Republic of Uzbekistan, education, spirituality, human consciousness, time, globalization.

In the era of globalization, increasing the morale of young people and guaranteeing their education have become an integral part of state policy. Especially increasing the activity of young people in the uncompromising fight against any negative evil is one of the pressing issues of the modern era. This process is inextricably linked with increasing legal consciousness and culture among all factors. Legal awareness and culture are an important criterion that determines a person's living on a legal and legal basis, significant prolongation of life, changes in his cultural and spiritual world. After all, the exemplary education of young people in any era depends on their knowledge and level, and constitutional knowledge plays an important role in the fight against their harmful vices.

From this point of view, the relevance of the ideas put forward in the context of our article is as follows:

First of all, since the majority of the population of our country is young people, measures are being taken to educate them. In general, the formation of legal consciousness and culture has risen to the level of state policy; in particular, the need to study the medical, social, educational and pedagogical aspects of the activities of young people who have a strong position in life is increasing.

Secondly, since a healthy life is directly related to the fight against any evil in society, education, culture and spirituality, it is important to study, analyze and find solutions to current problems of its development for young people.

Thirdly, the humanistic content of the life position is to strengthen a prosperous life, educate a mature generation, for this "... is developing measures aimed at legal education and training in educational institutions, improving the quality of professional training of specialists, and the constant improvement of educational programs" [1].

Creating a democratic legal state, the Republic of Uzbekistan considered one of its main tasks to be the formation of a highly educated, independent individual. To achieve this goal, first of all, consistent principles of state policy in the field of education were laid down.

Today, the scope of the organizational and legal framework for organizing the educational process has expanded significantly, that is, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Fight against Corruption" adopted on January 3, 2017 has further enriched this framework. The law consists of 6 chapters, 34 articles, and the 3rd chapter is called "Increasing legal awareness and legal culture in the field of combating corruption" [2]. Article 18 of this chapter is devoted to "Legal education and training in the field of combating corruption in educational institutions." According to its content, teachers and students, especially young people, should be intolerant of corruption during their activities and should contribute to the organization of many scientific and practical activities in this direction. Most importantly, the presence of important anti-corruption knowledge ensures the quality of professional training. The development of society and the fate of the next generation depend on the "flagship" of teachers and youth in the fight against harmful evil in society and a transparent attitude to each process.

In recent years, important practical work has been carried out in the education system, especially in higher education, within the framework of the conceptual idea of a "Corruption-Free System". In particular, in collaboration with the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the republic, the prosecutor's office, district activists, the women's committee and the television and radio company "We are against corruption!" and under the slogan "Education without corruption" various round tables, conferences, and events are held. Also in the field of higher education, clear examples of efforts in this direction are fair assessment of student knowledge, transparency, reducing types of control,

changing their type and digitalization of the system in order to prevent corruption.

Since the effect of any reforms is inextricably linked with financial support, regular increases in the monthly salaries of teachers and education system workers will ensure high-quality and productive work, preventing corruption in the field. In a word, “The large-scale reforms carried out in our country are supported by our people. The first results of these changes are clearly reflected in the life and daily life of our people, the social activity of our country, and confidence in the future is growing” [3].

According to our conclusion, the significance of the “On the Fight against Corruption” Law in the lives of young people can be seen in the following:

Firstly, youth education is linked to the fight against corruption, which opens up bright prospects for them.

Secondly, in the era of globalization, the further development of the educational mechanism and the introduction of the necessary new methods are associated with ensuring transparency, and long-term plans are implemented through this openness. This requires an in-depth study of the Law “On the Fight against Corruption”, the formation of legal consciousness and culture.

Thirdly, the education system, in particular higher education, “... takes the necessary measures to organize legal education and training, scientific and practical activities, and the development of educational, methodological and scientific literature” [4].

Therefore, each of us needs to mercilessly fight corruption. This struggle also represents our human duty.

Literatures:

- 1,2,4. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the fight against corruption”.
3. Message from the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. T.: Uzbekistan, 2018. Page 4.